

CLASSICA

Validating AI in classifying cancer in real-time surgery

D2.1 Final Clinical Validation Protocol, Patient Information Document, Consent Forms

Document date: 28 October 2022

Document version: 2.2

Deliverable No: D2.1

Dissemination Level: Public

Full Name	Short Name	Beneficiary Number	Role
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE DUBLIN, NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, DUBLIN	UCD	1	Coordinator
INSTITUT DE RECHERCHE CONTRE LES CANCERS DE L'APPAREIL DIGESTIF	IRCAD	2	Beneficiary
STICHTING E.A.E.S	EAES	3	Beneficiary
PINTAIL LTD	PT	4	Beneficiary
KOBENHAVNS UNIVERSITET	UCPH	5	Beneficiary
UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI TORINO	UNITO	6	Beneficiary
ZIEKENHUIS OOST-LIMBURG AUTONOME VERZORGINGSINSTELLING	ZOL	7	Beneficiary
ARCTUR RACUNALNISKI INZENIRING DOO	ARCTUR	8	Beneficiary
STICHTING VUMC	VUMC	9	Beneficiary
THE PENNSYLVANIA STATE UNIVERSITY	PSU	10	Beneficiary
KONVENT DER BARMHERZIGEN BRUDER GRAZ	BBGRAZ	11	Beneficiary

Executive Summary

Deliverable D2.1 details the study protocol, patient information leaflet and consent form for Study 1 of the CLASSICA project.

CLASSICA's work package (WP)2, 'Clinical Validation Preparation', has three objectives for ethical approval:

- To establish a robust trial governance framework
- To finalise the protocol for the clinical validation, including patient and consent documentation
- To secure ethical approval for each of the clinical sites

Study 1 of the project is a multicentre prospective observational study to confirm the validity and usability of previous findings of the developmental study (1). This study, performed at the Mater Hospital in Dublin, Ireland, outlined the use of artificial intelligence indocyanine green perfusion in classifying rectal cancers.

This deliverable is an output of Task 2.1 'Protocol and Documentation' and Task 2.1 'Trial Governance Framework'. The outputs from this deliverable will be used in Task 2.3 'Ethical approvals', where each site will apply individually for ethical approvals from relevant local or national bodies. As this is a multicentre study, the patient information leaflet and consent form have been written in the format required by the lead site, the Mater Hospital in Dublin, Ireland. It is proposed that these documents be used as a template for other sites and adapted and translated as required. This deliverable provides the complete documentation in the appendices.

The study protocol (Appendix 1) outlines the background and rationale behind the study itself. It also details inclusion and exclusion criteria and how the study will be performed at each site. Consideration of ethical issues, data management and protection is also given.

The patient information leaflet (Appendix 2) is the document that will be issued to participants in the study. It is split into six main parts: i) The Study, ii) Data Protection, iii) Costs, Funding and Approval, iv) Future Research, v) Further Information, and vi) Consent Form (Appendix 3). The objective of this document is to provide the relevant information to participants in a format that is clear to the layperson.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	2
List of acronyms, definitions, and abbreviations.....	4
1 Introduction.....	5
1.1 Introduction to CLASSICA	5
1.2 CLASSICA Study 1.....	5
2 Approach.....	6
2.1 Study protocol and patient information leaflets	6
3 Results.....	7
4 Impact & Conclusion	8
5 Appendices	9
5.1 Appendix 1 – Study Protocol	9
5.2 Participant Information Leaflet	21
5.3 Appendix 3 - Consent form.....	32

List of acronyms, definitions, and abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CRC	Clinical Research Centre
CT	Computerised Tomography
CTMP	Controlled Trial of Medicinal Product
EEA	European Economic Area
EU	European Union
FBC	Full Blood Count
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GP	General Practitioner
ICF	Informed Consent Form
ICG	Indocyanine Green
IFA	Intraoperative Fluorescence Angiography
LFT	Liver Function Test
MDR	Medical Devices Regulation
MRI	Magnetic Resonance Imaging
NIR	Near Infrared
OR	Operating Room
PIL	Patient Information Leaflet
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
TAMIS	Transanal Minimally Invasive Surgery
U&E	Urea and Electrolytes
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Introduction to CLASSICA

The Horizon Europe CLASSICA project will deliver and clinically validate an AI-based decision support technology, which allows rapid identification of the presence and distribution of cancer tumours. Validation will be carried out across several clinics, surgical teams, and countries.

Cancer and healthy tissue have radically different local blood perfusion patterns. This perfusion can be captured using near-infrared video after systemic fluorophore (indocyanine green) injection. Analysis of the footage can digitally identify cancer regions by tracking the perfusion over the initial seconds after dye administration by comparing the fluorescence signal in these areas with those in adjacent normal tissue within the same endolaparoscopic field of view. Application of AI methods (including computer vision and machine learning techniques) has enabled this differential classification to occur in real-time so that better, individualised surgical decisions can be taken during an operation

The CLASSICA AI-based technology will assist surgeons in real-time during operations by accurately identifying cancerous versus healthy tissue. A smart camera captures the tissue's colour changes during the procedure after administering a safe fluorescent dye. Video is processed by the AI, helping the surgeon to define the excision extent. This added support, combined with the surgeon's judgement and expertise, will minimise post-surgery complications and reduce the risk of cancer recurrence in the patient.

The specific objectives of the project are to:

- Deploy and carry out clinical validation studies across five clinical settings, including Ireland, Belgium, Austrian, Italy, and the Netherlands.
- Assess the usability, safety, and performance of the CLASSICA system.
- Agree on standard operating protocols for implementing and using the CLASSICA system.
- Develop and deliver training for CLASSICA tissue classification tools during biopsy and surgery.
- Develop new guidelines to help guide the use of AI for surgical decision support.

The project builds on breakthrough research by the Irish DTIF Consortium comprising UCD, RCSI and IBM Research, which developed the novel prototype that will be optimised and validated in the CLASSICA project.

1.2 CLASSICA Study 1

Clinical validation in CLASSICA will be possible through the implementation of three studies. The clinical validation involves five clinical sites sharing patient data and video from procedures using approved near-infrared (NIR) fluorescence to enhance the intraoperative clinical care of patients with significant rectal polyps. Included in this deliverable are the study protocol, patient information leaflet and consent form for Study 1.

Study 1 of the CLASSICA project is a prospective observational validation study aiming to demonstrate the validity, generalisability and usability of the outcomes of a previous developmental study carried

out in the Mater Hospital (UCD)¹. This study, carried out prior to CLASSICA, demonstrated the feasibility of using AI alongside indocyanine fluorescence perfusion imaging to classify rectal tumours. Study 1 in CLASSICA will verify the validity, usability and generalisability of the tissue classification technology, including the optimisations made to the technology in WP1 ‘AI system refinement and support’. This study is a key CLASSICA output and will allow for progression to Study 2. This study has been designed as a multicentre study to demonstrate that the same technology can be rolled out in multiple sites with reasonable efficiency – a demonstration of usability, and that the findings of the original study hold across different patient populations – a demonstration of generalisability. This generalisability is of particular relevance given the use of AI in this projection. The more heterogenous the dataset used to develop the algorithm is, the more generalisable it should be to a different patient population.

Study 1 and ethical preparation are carried out under WP2, ‘Clinical Validation Preparation’, which UCD leads with support from the CLASSICA Trial Management Group.

Deliverable 2.2 focuses on delivering the study protocol and patient information leaflets. These documents form the foundation of the practical application of the study principles to each clinical site. They are also a key component of the applications for ethical approval at each site (D2.2).

2 Approach

2.1 Study protocol and patient information leaflets

The study protocol gives a detailed description of how exactly each step of the study is to be performed at each site. As this is a validation study, the same protocol must be followed at each site to ensure the accuracy and generalisability of the results. This ensures uniformity between clinical sites.

The patient information leaflet and consent form allow for appropriate consent from study participants. For this consent to be considered informed, the information leaflet is provided to patients following a discussion of involvement in the study with a member of the research team. This allows the patient an appropriate time to consider their inclusion in the study. It is essential that this document is written in a patient-appropriate language without unnecessary medical terminology or jargon. This document aims to explain the rationale and clinical need behind the project to potential participants. This document also describes in detail what will be involved in taking part in the study and what implications it may have for the participant. It also includes information on how to withdraw from the study should they wish to do so.

UCD initially drafted these documents. Previous protocols, patient information leaflets and consent forms utilised in the CLASSICA developmental study were used as a reference and updated as necessary.

¹ Cahill RA, O’Shea DF, Khan MF, Khokhar HA, Epperlein JP, Mac Aonghusa PG, et al. Artificial intelligence indocyanine green (ICG) perfusion for colorectal cancer intra-operative tissue classification. *Br J Surg.* 2021;108(1):5-9.

3 Results

The complete documentation is attached in the appendices to this deliverable. This includes the study protocol (Appendix 1), patient information leaflet (Appendix 2), and consent forms (Appendix 3) as they apply to the Mater Hospital (UCD).

Study 1 of the CLASSICA project is a validation study designed to validate the results of the previous developmental study by UCD. The **study protocol** provides a lay summary of the study, background and rationale, a detailed description of study objectives, outcome measures and design, participant identification, treatment of study subjects, safety reporting, statistical analysis, data management, ethics, financing and study reporting. The objective of this document is to provide a clear structure to the study, which should be followed in each clinical site to ensure the validity of the results. The aims of this study are outlined below :

- **Study aim 1:** To deploy our novel real-time classification technology in five distinct clinical settings (Ireland, Belgium, Austria, Italy and the Netherlands) and to verify that surgical teams at each site can successfully use the system (usability). *Metric: systems established and tested on-site; surgical teams trained are successfully using CLASSICA.*
- **Study aim 2:** To assess the usability, safety and performance of the CLASSICA in multiple clinical environments. *Metric: completed clinical validation, review of performance across patient populations, process evaluation and stakeholder (surgeon) feedback.*
- **Study aim 3:** To create agreed standard operating protocols for the creation, interpretation and use of CLASSICA information by surgeons. *Metric: agreed SOP texts, SOPs followed throughout clinical validation*
- **Study aim 4:** To develop new guidelines related to the use of AI for surgical decision support in operations in Europe, including video databanks for their development and validation. *Metric: new clinical guidelines drafted*
- **Study aim 5:** To ensure and verify full compliance with relevant EU regulatory frameworks, notably those covering data management (e.g., GDPR) and those addressing medical devices (CE marking, EU-MDR)

Six hundred patients will be recruited in total, 120 at each study site. Participating clinicians will identify these patients through outpatient clinics, endoscopy, and multi-disciplinary team meetings. Patients with rectal tumours greater than 2 cm and those with confirmed rectal cancers undergoing surgical assessment or intervention will be eligible for inclusion. Patients with a contraindication to the administration of ICG, those unable to provide informed consent and pregnant or breastfeeding women will be excluded. Patients will undergo an examination under anaesthesia, as is the standard of care. As part of this examination, and for the purposes of the study, patients will then undergo an ICG assessment of the tumour. Following IV injection of ICG, fluorescence is detected via an infrared camera and the pattern of fluorescence is recorded. At this point, the patient proceeds to resection of the tumour as clinically indicated, and no further intervention is required from a trial perspective. The intra-operative video is then pseudonymised and sent to Arctur. Arctur will use these videos to examine the subtle differences in fluorescence emission seen between cancerous and non-cancerous tissue and, building on the previous algorithms developed by IBM in the developmental study, create a software programme capable of accurately distinguishing between cancerous and non-cancerous tissue based on these fluorescence patterns.

The **patient information leaflet** is divided into five sections: i) study description, ii) data protection, iii) costs, funding and approval, iv) future research, and v) further information. Each of these sections is designed to be read by patients and so have been written in lay terms. The objective of this document is to provide patients with enough information about the study to make an informed decision on whether to participate.

The **consent form** completes the patient information leaflet. It provides written documentation that the patient has understood what is entailed in the study and has given their consent for participation.

Each clinical site (UNITO, ZOL, VUmc, BBGRAZ) will adapt its own proforma with the appropriate translation.

4 Impact & Conclusion

The work reported here allows each site to begin the process of applying for ethical approval. This work is an output of WP2 and provides the necessary documentation for ethical approval. This deliverable formalises the structure of the study across each clinical site.

Successful completion of Study 1 will demonstrate the validity of our previous developmental study and therefore establish that patterns of ICG fluorescence may be used to differentiate cancer and non-cancer cells by means of artificial intelligence. Successful implementation of this across multiple sites involving different patient populations will demonstrate both the usability and generalisability of the software.

Completing Study 1 will allow us to progress to Studies 2 and 3 of the project. Study 2 compares biopsies taken with guidance from the novel software developed as a result of Study 1 with traditional biopsies. In contrast, Study 3 is a randomised controlled trial comparing the quality of excision margins between patients undergoing standard transanal excision of rectal tumours and those undergoing excision guided by fluorescence-based software. Each of these studies relies on the foundations of the software built in Study 1. Throughout these two studies, ongoing improvements and refinements of the software will be made. Continuous feedback will be given by stakeholders at each site as to the performance of the software to continue to develop it as the project progresses to Studies 2 and 3.

Experiences gained in Study 1 will allow for the drafting of agreed standard operating protocols for the creation, interpretation and use of CLASSICA information by surgeons. It will ultimately provide the foundation for developing new guidelines for using AI for surgical decision support.

In conclusion, the protocol, patient information leaflet and consent form provide the framework for the successful completion of Study 1, which provides the basis for progression to Studies 2 and 3 and, therefore, for completion of the overall project and accomplishments of the study objectives as outlined above.

5 Appendices

5.1 Appendix 1 – Study Protocol

CLASSICA: Validating AI in Classifying Cancer in Real-Time Surgery

Date and Version No: 2.0 26/09/2022

Chief Investigator: Ronan Cahill, Consultant Surgeon Mater Misericordiae University Hospital, Mater Private Hospital and Full Professor (University College Dublin)

Funder: European Union - Horizon Europe

Chief Investigator Signature: The approved protocol should be signed by the author(s) and/or person(s) authorised to sign the protocol

No potential conflicts of interest related to this project.

RC is named on a patent filed in relation to processes for visual determination of tissue biology and receives speaker fees from Stryker Corp and research funding from Intuitive Corp.

Contents

Executive Summary	2
List of acronyms, definitions, and abbreviations	4
1 Introduction.....	5
1.1 Introduction to CLASSICA	5
1.2 CLASSICA Study 1.....	5
2 Approach	6
2.1 Study protocol and patient information leaflets	6
3 Results.....	7
4 Impact & Conclusion	8
5 Appendices	9
5.1 Appendix 1 – Study Protocol	9
5.1.1 KEY STUDY CONTACTS	11
5.1.2 BACKGROUND AND RATIONALE.....	12
5.1.3 OBJECTIVES AND OUTCOME MEASURES.....	13
5.1.4 STUDY DESIGN	14
5.1.5 PARTICIPANT IDENTIFICATION	14
5.1.5.1 Study Participants.....	14
5.1.5.2 Inclusion Criteria.....	14
5.1.5.3 Exclusion Criteria	15
5.1.6 TREATMENT OF STUDY SUBJECTS	15
5.1.6.1 Participant recruitment and screening.....	15
5.1.6.2 Informed Consent.....	15
5.1.6.3 Baseline measurements	16
5.1.6.4 Diagnostic intervention	16
5.1.6.5 Preparation.....	16
5.1.6.6 Tumour characteristic recording	16
5.1.6.7 Biopsies and Tissue Analysis.....	17
5.1.6.8 Video analysis	17
5.1.6.9 Sample Handling.....	17
5.1.6.10 Early Discontinuation/Withdrawal of Participants.....	17
5.1.7 SAFETY REPORTING	18
5.1.8 STATISTICS	18
5.1.9 DATA HANDLING AND RECORD KEEPING	18
5.1.10 RETENTION OF ESSENTIAL DOCUMENTS.....	19
5.1.11 QUALITY ASSURANCE PROCEDURES	19
5.1.12 PROTOCOL DEVIATIONS	19
5.1.13 ETHICS.....	19
5.1.14 FINANCING AND INSURANCE/INDEMNITY	19
5.1.15 SUB - APPENDIX A: SCHEDULE OF PROCEDURES.....	20
5.2 Appendix 2 – Patient Information Leaflet (see attached file)	21

5.2.1	Part 1 – The Study	22
5.2.1.1	Why is this study being done?.....	22
5.2.1.2	Why have I been invited to take part?	23
5.2.1.3	Do I have to take part? Can I withdraw?	23
5.2.1.4	What happens if I change my mind?.....	23
5.2.1.5	How will the study be carried out?	24
5.2.1.6	What will happen to me if I decide to take part?.....	24
5.2.1.7	What will happen to my Samples and Data?	25
5.2.1.8	Are there any benefits to taking part in this research?.....	26
5.2.1.9	Are there any risks to me or others if I take part?	27
5.2.1.10	What happens if something goes wrong when I’m taking part in the study?	27
5.2.1.11	Will I be told the outcome of the study? Will I be told the results of any tests or investigations performed as part of this study that relate to me?	27
5.2.2	Part 2 – Data Protection	27
5.2.2.1	What information about me (personal data) will be used in this study? Will my medical records be accessed?.....	28
5.2.2.2	What will happen to my personal data?	28
5.2.2.3	Who will access and use my personal data as part of this study?	28
5.2.2.4	Will my personal data be kept confidential? How will my data be kept safe?	29
5.2.2.5	What is the lawful basis for using my personal data?.....	29
5.2.2.6	What are my rights?	29
5.2.3	Part 3 – Costs, Funding and Approval	30
5.2.3.1	Has this study been approved by a research ethics committee?.....	30
5.2.3.2	Who is organising and funding this study? Will the results be used for commercial purposes?	30
5.2.3.3	Is there any payment for taking part? Will it cost me anything if I agree to take part?	30
5.2.4	Part 4 – Future Research	30
5.2.4.1	Will my personal data and/or biological material be used in future studies?	30
5.2.5	Part 5 – Further Information	31
5.2.5.1	Who should I contact for information or complaints?	31
5.2.5.2	Will I be contacted again?	31
5.3	Appendix 3 - Consent form (see attached file).....	32

5.1.1 KEY STUDY CONTACTS

Chief Investigator	Prof Ronan Cahill UCD School of Medicine, Mater Private Hospital Tel: 01-7164597 Email: ronan.cahill@ucd.ie
---------------------------	--

Sponsor	University College Dublin
Funder(s)	EU Horizon Europe
Centre	UCD Clinical Research Centre
Contact	

Study Title	CLASSICA: Validating AI in Classifying Cancer in Real-Time Surgery
Internal ref. no. (or short title)	To be Confirmed
Study registration	To be Confirmed
Sponsor	University College Dublin
Funder	EU Horizon Europe
Clinical Phase	
Study Design	Prospective Observational Cohort
Study Participants	Patients with or suspected of having rectal cancer undergoing endoscopic investigation or intervention as part of their standard care.
Sample Size	600 patients
Planned Study Period	38 months. For any single patient, involvement relates to the day of investigation/intervention alone. Follow-up via medical records will be concluded within 30 days of the procedure.
Planned Recruitment period	1 st October 2022 – 1 st December 2025

5.1.2 BACKGROUND AND RATIONALE

Rectal polyps >2cm in size (affecting c. 10,000 patients a year in Europe alone) represent a considerable clinical challenge. While smaller polyps can be addressed by routine endoscopic polypectomy and frank clinical cancer will advance through a traditional cancer surgery paradigm, polyps of this size have the option of being locally excised, intact by transanal endoscopic resection (also referred to as Transanal Minimally Invasive Surgery, TAMIS). This is the treatment of choice in this site due to its ability to provide a single complete unfragmented specimen versus other modalities (e.g. endoscopic submucosal resection). The technology and training to enable transanal resection has become much more available over the past decade (especially TAMIS), meaning more patients can have large benign lesions. Even early rectal cancers can now be excised in their local specialist centres. Therefore, the major breakthrough in such care is patient selection: i.e. how to tell if a given patient has a benign polyp or a cancer in advance of its resection.

Endoscopic biopsies are notoriously inaccurate in up to 20% of such lesions (rectal cancers often commence as adenomatous lesions, so superficial biopsies may miss a malignant focus). Mistakenly

identifying a cancer as a benign lesion and treating it by local excision significantly worsens prognosis and compromises subsequent cancer surgery - including potentially converting a reconstructable site of resection (i.e. a lesion suitable for anterior resection) to a non-reconstructable one (i.e. needing an abdominoperineal resection with permanent colostomy) and by seeding cancer cells into a deep margin or different plane, particularly as in the case for anteriorly positioned lesions. Additionally, transanal excision techniques continue to have relatively high rates of positive margins; this risks regrowth in benign lesions and limits effective local therapy for earliest-stage cancers due to the presence of inapparent disease close to the main tumour bulk.

We have previously demonstrated, through the use of fluorescent indocyanine green (ICG), that perfusion is visibly different between tumour and healthy tissue. This difference can be captured via infrared video, and mathematical analysis can differentiate the perfusion pattern of malignant areas from any benign/normal tissue visible in the same endoscopic view. Therefore, video analysis can be used to distinguish between healthy and cancerous tissues in a location (such as the rectum) where a cancer is suspected. This discovery can be exploited for clinical use by applying AI methods, including computer vision and machine learning. In essence, the fluorescence intensity of pixels displaying tissues of interest varies with blood flow (perfusion) when the blood is dyed with ICG and lit by near-infra-red (NIR) light. The intensity is captured over time from multiple video frames, and this intensity is plotted as a curve. The intensity curves of tumour tissue differ from those of healthy tissue, and those of benign tumours differ from malignant ones. Analysis of the curve features for each pixel in a region of interest can thus lead to a classification.

Such an AI system has been prototyped and trained in the Mater Hospital with videos from a population of Irish cancer patients from two regional centres to automatically identify malignant tumours and benign lesions from healthy tissue by their perfusion patterns. The system can be run within the OR (on a laptop, connected to an imaging probe with a camera, or within some future OR apparatus). A surgeon can position the camera to capture the region of interest, trigger the release of fluorescent dye, and then receive specific cancer/healthy information about the tissues, especially polyps.

In this study, we clinically validate this prototype and its underlying AI, addressing the question of generalisability, i.e. can other surgeons use the system and get similar results from their specific patient cohorts? This will pave the way for future studies which are planned to determine the roles of biopsy (can the system enable optimal choice of biopsied tissue, and thus reduce biopsy error?); and tumour resection (can the system increase the completeness and accuracy of tumour resection?).

5.1.3 OBJECTIVES AND OUTCOME MEASURES

Study aim 1: To deploy our novel real-time classification technology in five distinct clinical settings (Ireland, Belgium, Austria, Italy and the Netherlands) and to verify that surgical teams at each site can successfully use the system (usability). *Metric: systems established and tested on-site; surgical teams trained are successfully using CLASSICA.*

Study aim 2: To assess the usability, safety and performance of the CLASSICA in multiple clinical environments. *Metric: completed clinical validation, review of performance across patient populations, process evaluation and stakeholder (surgeon) feedback.*

Study aim 3: To create agreed standard operating protocols for the creation, interpretation and use of CLASSICA information by surgeons. *Metric: agreed SOP texts, SOPs followed throughout clinical validation*

Study aim 4: To develop new guidelines related to the use of AI for surgical decision support in operations in Europe, including the use of video databanks for their development and validation. *Metric: new clinical guidelines drafted*

Study aim 5: To ensure and verify full compliance with relevant EU regulatory frameworks, notably those covering data management (e.g. GDPR) and those addressing medical devices (CE marking, EU-MDR)

5.1.4 STUDY DESIGN

This is a prospective, unblinded, non-CTMP, multicentre observational study to validate the use of ICG IFA with AI analytics to differentiate areas of cancer vs areas of non-cancer within a rectal polyp. Trans-anal surgery will be performed via a minimally invasive fashion, whether by a laparoscopic or robotic technique, depending on surgeon preference, as part of a diagnostic or therapeutic intervention in the standard way based on the patient's clinical need. During the procedure, indocyanine green (ICG) will be administered by peripheral cannula. The area of interest will be examined using a near-infrared scope to determine the presence, persistence and inflow/outflow pathways of the dye. The video image will be subjected to further analysis by computer vision and data analytics for the purposes of elucidating specific patterns enabling machine learning to build algorithms for flow characterisation informed by biophysics and pseudo-anonymised clinical data.

In all, 600 patients will be studied over the four-year period across the multiple sites. It is anticipated that approximately 120 patients will be recruited at each site. However, this may vary depending on each site. The study may be completed earlier if a site recruits more patients.

There are no follow-up visits for this study. Follow-up data will be obtained from medical charts. The trial will not be blinded to participants, medical staff, or clinical trial staff.

5.1.5 PARTICIPANT IDENTIFICATION

5.1.5.1 Study Participants

Participants with a confirmed or suspected rectal polyp/tumour measuring greater than 2cm. Clinically fit for elective intervention and meeting inclusion/exclusion criteria.

5.1.5.2 Inclusion Criteria

- The participant is willing and able to give informed consent for participation in the study.
- Male or Female, aged 18 years or above.
- Clinical features suspicious of or diagnosed with a rectal polyp/tumour measuring >2cm

5.1.5.3 Exclusion Criteria

The participant may not enter the study if ANY of the following apply:

- Female participant who is pregnant, lactating or planning pregnancy within three months of the study
- Significant renal or hepatic impairment.
- Any other significant disease or disorder which, in the opinion of the Investigator, may either put the participants at risk because of participation in the study or may influence the result of the study or the participant's ability to participate in the study.
- Allergy to an intravenous contrast agent or iodides
- Other contraindications to ICG including concurrent use of anticonvulsants, bisulphite containing drugs, methadone and nitrofurantoin

5.1.6 TREATMENT OF STUDY SUBJECTS

5.1.6.1 Participant recruitment and screening

Adult patients with a suspected diagnosis of a rectal polyp/tumour undergoing diagnostics or therapeutic intervention by trans-anal minimally invasive surgery will be approached for inclusion in the trial. Participants must be able and willing to comply with the terms of the protocol.

Such patients will be identified from referral letters, outpatient clinics, endoscopy lists, and multidisciplinary cancer meetings. Patients will undergo standard preoperative work-up, including but not limited to colonic visualisation by either colonoscopy or CT colonogram, staging CT scan of the chest, abdomen and pelvis, MRI of the rectum, and assessment of fitness for surgery as per standard practice. The optimal management of the patient will be determined based on institutional protocols.

Suitability for inclusion as per the selection criteria in section 5 will be assessed, and patients will be provided with verbal and written details.

5.1.6.2 Informed Consent

A verbal explanation of the study, along with the approved Patient Information Leaflet (PIL)/ Informed Consent Form (ICF), will be provided by a suitably qualified member of the healthcare team for the patient to consider. The PIL will provide detailed information about the rationale, design and personal implications of the study. Following the information provision, patients will be given the opportunity to discuss the study with their family and healthcare professionals and will be given as much time as possible to consider their participation in the study; ideally they will be allowed 24 hours as a minimum. The right of the patient to refuse consent without given reasons will be respected. Patients will then be formally assessed for eligibility and invited to provide informed, written consent for their participation in the study. Patients are able to withdraw their participation at any time without giving a reason. A copy of the signed consent form will be given to the participant. The original signed form will be retained at the study site.

5.1.6.3 Baseline measurements

Participants undergoing colorectal surgery undergo a standard preoperative work-up which may include colonic visualisation by either colonoscopy or computerised tomogram (CT) colonogram, staging CT scan of the chest, abdomen and pelvis, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) of the rectum, and assessment of fitness for surgery. All baseline assessments performed will be part of standard preoperative procedures during the first two days before diagnostic endoscopy or surgery. Haematological and biochemistry blood testing (full blood count, FBC, liver function test (LFTs) & Urea and Electrolytes (U&Es) are routinely anyway performed prior to treatment. Patients undergoing diagnostic evaluation alone may not have all these studies routinely completed before this. Still, for this study's purposes, they will have their haematological and biochemical testing advanced before intervention.

5.1.6.4 Diagnostic intervention

5.1.6.5 Preparation

Standard endoscopic evaluation will be performed using either a robotic or laparoscopic endoscope with the transanally white light assessment of the bowel segment. This will be followed by a near-infrared evaluation of the tissue of interest after systemic administration of ICG at 0.25 mg/kg body weight for 5 minutes to allow both inflow and outflow to be visualised. An access method (e.g. Lone Star retractor, GelPOINT Path, or TEO rectoscope) may be needed to ensure appropriate visualisation. Trauma to the area should be avoided to minimise bleeding, as this may disturb the infrared video. Prior to the procedure, the 25 mg vial of ICG should be fully reconstituted in 10 ml of water for injection (NOT saline) to give an injectable concentration of 2.5 mg/ml.

(ICG available through a pharmacy as 25 mg vial. Trade name Verdye)

The required i.v. dose is calculated at 0.25 mg/kg.

- o Example: 80kg patient = 80 (kg) x 0.25 (mg/kg) = 20 mg total dose.
- o $20 \div 2.5$ (mg/ml premade solution) = 8 ml dose of pre-prepared ICG solution to be given as bolus dose

5.1.6.6 Tumour characteristic recording

- a) The lesion of interest should ideally be fully visualised within the field of view seen on the monitor (partial visualisation of lesion also acceptable).
- b) Lesion and surrounding control tissue should be free from debris and blood as far as possible. Wash with saline, water, or gauze if needed before ICG administration.
- c) The near-infra-red camera should be perpendicular to the lesion of interest, ideally with some adjacent normal control tissue (may not be achievable with larger lesions). Ensure all theatre lights are off.
- d) Recording should take place in NIR mode – ensure NIR mode is activated prior to ICG administration (button 1 on Novadaq Pinpoint system) and recording is on.

- e) Once satisfactory positioning has been achieved, and all instruments have been removed from the field of view, the required dose of ICG solution should be given as a bolus intravenous dose. Anaesthetic lines may require flushing with water for injection to ensure rapid administration of the full dose.
- f) 20-40 seconds following administration, an increased fluorescence signal should be seen on the screen. Camera movement and any external disruption (introduction of instruments etc.) should be avoided as much as possible. Do not attempt to re-adjust camera positioning once ICG inflow has begun.
- g) 5 minutes of uninterrupted recording is ideal; however, the duration may change based on clinical circumstances.

Following this, the procedure may continue in the normal fashion. Additional biopsies may be taken at the discretion of the operating surgeon.

Local anaesthetic agents containing adrenaline should be avoided during the procedure as they typically contain sodium metabisulphite as a preservative which may interact with ICG.

5.1.6.7 Biopsies and Tissue Analysis

In addition to that needed for standard pathological assessment, some additional samples may be taken in order to map with precision the fluorescence pattern across the tumour area

5.1.6.8 Video analysis

Video recording from the intervention will be studied by investigators at UCD, ensured free of any personal identifying information and subjected to annotation to clarify regions of interest throughout the recording. The pseudonymised information (including clinical classifiers) will be shared with researchers at Arctur and other collaborating institutions, in whose hands it will be anonymous, in accordance with best GDPR practice.

The schedule of participant-focussed procedures is shown in Appendix A.

5.1.6.9 Sample Handling

The majority of samples referred to in the protocol are taken as part of a standard of care pathway, with the results accessed by the research team. Research samples, including video recordings for analysis under this protocol, will be processed and stored within the UCD Clinical Research Centre/Centre for Precision Surgery and Department of Pathology, [insert hospital name]. Only defined researchers working on this project as part of the study team will have access to the samples.

Tissue slides, videos and clinical data will be stored for 10 years in a secure location in the [insert hospital name] and UCD Clinical Research Centre.

5.1.6.10 Early Discontinuation/Withdrawal of Participants

During the course of the study, a participant may choose to withdraw early from the study treatment at any time. This may happen for a number of reasons, including but not limited to the following:

- Inability to comply with study procedures
- Participant decision

Participants may also withdraw their consent, meaning they wish to completely withdraw from the study. Complete Participant withdrawal from the study with the withdrawal of all the data and samples collected up until the point of withdrawal is not possible with respect to pseudoanonymised data generated by that time in order for use for MI classifiers as such data submitted is no longer traceable back to the participant.

In addition, the Investigator may discontinue a participant from the study treatment at any time if the Investigator considers it necessary for any reason including, but not limited to:

- Pregnancy
- Ineligibility (either arising during the study or retrospectively having been overlooked at screening)
- Significant protocol deviation
- Significant non-compliance with treatment regimen or study requirements

Follow-up of participants who have withdrawn from treatment will consist of standard clinical care. The type of withdrawal and reason for withdrawal will be recorded in the CRF.

5.1.7 SAFETY REPORTING

We do not anticipate any significant adverse events during the course of this study. However, any adverse events that do occur at any site during the course of the study will be reported to the Principle Investigator and to the sponsor.

5.1.8 STATISTICS

A detailed Statistical Analysis Plan will be developed in collaboration with the Study partners in conjunction with the study biostatistician.

5.1.9 DATA HANDLING AND RECORD KEEPING

All data management for this study will be conducted according to UCD Clinical Research Centre Standard Operating Procedures. A detailed Data Management Plan will be developed.

Videos recorded during diagnostic assessment or surgery will be pseudonymised to contain no personal identifying information, including external characteristics capable of identification. Videos will be transferred from the endolaparoscopic visual processing unit for secure transfer via encrypted USB and/or digital operating platform with a doubly backup recording kept on a dedicated computer in a secure location within the UCD Centre for Precision Surgery.

Relevant patient details (age, cancer stage and type, clinical course, co-morbidities, and intraoperative haemodynamic characteristics) will be stored in a password-protected database linked to the video. Transfer for analytics will be done by secure encrypted upload. Non-identifiable categorical classifying information (such as cancer/benign or complicated/not complicated) will be shared. No personally identifiable data will be transferred outside the institution (all such details will be pseudonymised by designated clinical staff working on the project in line with the hospital's GDPR best practice recommendations, so only coded clinical data will be sent outside the institution).

Video analysis will be performed initially by Arctur, Nova Gorica, Slovenia. Additional formal collaborating partners may be agreed upon and will follow the same protocol.

Video and coded clinical data transferred to another organisation will only be used for the purpose of the project and will be deleted at the point of study conclusion. Data will be retained at UCD/CRC for 10 years. Data at other sites will be destroyed.

Videos may be stored long-term for use in future ethically approved studies in a secure location in the UCD Centre for Precision Surgery/Clinical Research Centre.

5.1.10 RETENTION OF ESSENTIAL DOCUMENTS

All data and metadata relating to the study will be retained at the CRC for 10 years following publication. This includes case report forms in addition to intra-operative videos. This will be stored on an encrypted hard drive stored in a secure location within the CRC.

5.1.11 QUALITY ASSURANCE PROCEDURES

The study will be conducted in accordance with the currently approved protocol, GCP, relevant regulations and standard operating procedures. A risk assessment and monitoring plan will be prepared before the study opens and will be reviewed as necessary to reflect significant changes to the protocol or outcomes of monitoring activities. The Sponsor, University College Dublin, will conduct the risk assessment.

5.1.12 PROTOCOL DEVIATIONS

A study-related deviation is a departure from the ethically approved study protocol, other study document, process, or applicable regulatory requirements. Any deviations from the protocol will be documented in a protocol deviation form and filed in the study master file.

5.1.13 ETHICS

A full ethical application will be made to the relevant body at each clinical site (e.g. the Local Ethics Committee at the Mater Hospital) under the guidance of the research team at the Clinical Research Centre in the Mater Hospital.

5.1.14 FINANCING AND INSURANCE/INDEMNITY

Funding of €6 million has been granted through the EU Horizon Europe program. This will be sufficient to cover the costs associated with the study. Indemnity has previously been secured in relation to the previous developmental study through the Clinical Research Centre at UCD and is anticipated to be expanded to this study.

5.1.15 SUB - APPENDIX A: SCHEDULE OF PROCEDURES

Procedures	Visits 3 to coincide with clinical care				
	Visit timing Visit 1 Outpatients Clinic	Visit 2 Preop Visit	Visit 3 Day of Intervention/Day of Surgery	Visit 4 Postop Days 1-5	Follow-up (medical chart)
	Screening	Baseline			
Informed consent	*	*			
Demographics	*				
Medical history	*				
Concomitant medications	*				
Physical examination	*				
ECG		*			
Laboratory tests (routine)		*	*	*	*
Eligibility assessment	*				
Dispensing of study drugs			*		
Confirmation of Consent		*	*		
Preoperative administration of ICG (subgroup) & non- invasive plasma clearance		*			
Intraoperative administration of ICG			*		
Intraprocedural observation and fluorescence measurement inc plasma clearance, stereotactic visualisation			*		
Video Recording of Endolaparoscopic View			*		

Appendix 2 – Patient Information Leaflet

5.2 Participant Information Leaflet

Name of Study: CLASSICA: Validating Mathematical Methods and Artificial Intelligence in for the classification of cancer-based on fluorescence perfusion patterns.

Site	Mater Misericordiae University Hospital [insert local site as applicable]
Principal Investigator(s) and Co-Investigator(s) (insert names, titles and contact details)	Prof. Ronan Cahill, Consultant General and Colorectal Surgeon at MMUH, Professor of Surgery at UCD
Study Organiser/ Sponsor (if applicable)	University College Dublin
Data Controllers	University College Dublin Mater Misericordiae University Hospital
Data Protection Officer	University College Dublin: gdp@ucd.ie [insert local DPO], e.g.: The Mater Hospital: dataprotection@mater.ie or 01 803 4311

You have been invited to take part in a research study called “CLASSICA: Validating Mathematical Methods & Artificial Intelligence for the Classification of Cancer Based on Fluorescence Perfusion Patterns”.

Before you decide if you want to take part, we would like to explain to you why the research is being done, how we will use your information, and what the study involves. Please read this information carefully. Ask us if anything is unclear or if you would like more information. Don't feel rushed or under pressure to make a quick decision. It would be best if you understood the risks and benefits of taking part in this study so that you can make a decision that is right for you. You may wish to discuss it with your family, friends or GP.

This leaflet has five main parts:

Part 1 – The Study

Part 2 – Data Protection

Part 3 – Costs, Funding and Approval

Part 4 – Future Research

Part 5 – Further Information

5.2.1 Part 1 – The Study

5.2.1.1 Why is this study being done?

This study is for people having a “keyhole” investigation or surgery for large bowel diseases (both the colon and the rectum). Such investigation or surgery uses a camera placed internally that enables the surgeon to see a person’s interior to identify the disease and move surgical equipment during the procedure to take a sample of it or even remove it. The pictures and video from the camera are transferred through a computer to a screen for the surgeon to see. In this study, we will look at 600 patients across different hospitals to see if these videos and pictures can be analysed in a more sophisticated way using tissue perfusion analysis. Tissues are parts of the body that work together to perform a specific function in the body. Perfusion analysis means we will examine how blood flows through the tissues of your colon or rectum in these videos using software and mathematical methods. We want to see if this extra information could be useful in guiding surgeons to make decisions in surgery.

Understanding the nature of body tissues during operations is a really important part of the surgery. Sometimes we need to decide if the tissue contains cancerous cells, and if so, how much. The better the surgeon is able to understand the nature of any abnormal tissue, the better the result for the patient. This is true at the time a cancer is first seen or when something unexpected is seen during surgery being performed for the disease. We want to develop visual tools to help decision-making during the investigation or surgery, including where samples are taken, the urgency of their analysis and even the best way to remove the disease fully.

Cancer development depends on and is impacted by the local blood supply to tissues. In this study, we will use a dye to reveal the blood flow at a small blood vessel level, together with a camera that sensitively recognises this dye during your operation. We will analyse this video after the surgery with the help of our partner Arctur, a software company based in Slovenia. And also using methods we have previously developed with IBM Research (who are consultants in the project). Together we will use mathematical methods and computer software to evaluate how accurate such video analysis can be for characterising the nature of the tissue seen during the operation. Some tissues samples will also be studied to make sure what we see in the pictures reflects what is happening in the tissues. However, we will not be changing your intervention overall from the current standard of care. The additional steps are

for research purposes only, and your clinical team will not use the information for your care during this study.

A smaller, similar study has already been carried out in the Mater Hospital on this topic. Thanks to the participation of previous patients, we have shown that a computer programme can accurately tell cancer cells from non-cancer cells. The next step is to make sure this applies on a larger scale with a diverse group of patients – that is why we are performing this study in multiple hospitals throughout Europe, including more patients from Ireland. If our early findings hold true, then this has a lot of potentials to help other patients with rectal disease, but this is something that, at the moment, we do not know.

5.2.1.2 Why have I been invited to take part?

You are being asked to participate in this research study as you have or may have a polyp or tumour of your rectum, which needs a procedure to evaluate or remove. We hope to recruit 120 patients in the [insert hospital name] and a further 320 patients across the other hospitals participating in this study. All of these patients will be chosen on the basis that they have either a polyp or tumour of the rectum.

5.2.1.3 Do I have to take part? Can I withdraw?

No, you do not have to take part. Participation in any study, including this one, is voluntary. If you do decide to take part, you may withdraw your consent to take part at any time without giving us a reason. Your doctor will not be upset if you decide not to take part. Your treatment and care will not be affected if you decide not to participate in this study.

If you decide to participate, you will be given this information document to keep. You will be asked to sign a consent form to document your understanding of the study and your agreement to take part. If you wish to withdraw from the study, please contact our Clinical Research [insert contact details of site-specific nurse or point of contact]

5.2.1.4 What happens if I change my mind?

If you change your mind about being in the study after it has started, you can withdraw from the study at any time. If you choose to withdraw from this study before your sample or video has been made, none of your data will be included in the study. Suppose you choose to withdraw after your sample and video recording have already been processed. In that case, your data generated will already have been used for analysis, and it will not be possible to withdraw it at that stage. However, should there be any remaining sample(s) or if the video recording has not been analysed, these will be discarded appropriately. This will not affect the standard of care you will receive. Your doctor will not be upset that you have chosen to withdraw from the study.

5.2.1.5 How will the study be carried out?

This study will take place in the Mater hospital, Dublin and in five other hospitals in Europe for approximately four years commencing in late 2022. We plan to involve 600 patients in total in this study across multiple hospitals in Europe. Approximately 120 of these patients will come from those attending the [insert hospital name]. All patients participating in the study are undergoing investigation of or treatment for a rectal polyp or tumour. Following standard pre-operative work-up, patients will have their clinical care carried out as planned in accordance with the current standard of care. In addition, for this study, at the time of the investigation or treatment, patients will be given an intravenous injection of dye called indocyanine green (ICG). At the same time, they are asleep under general anaesthetic. Video recordings will be taken to show how the dye is being taken up in the tumour or polyp compared to the normal healthy tissue beside it. The video taken during the operation, along with some broad details about you (no personally identifying data), will be analysed by a computer to see if the computer can detect areas of cancer within the polyp. We will look at it mathematically ourselves as researchers to understand how exactly the computer is making these decisions. These analyses will later be compared to the analysis performed by the pathologist to see if the computer system can accurately tell the difference between cancer and non-cancer cells. The same video and broad details will also be used to see if an automatic method of such analysis can be constructed. This will be needed in future studies to move this towards clinical practice. As mentioned above, this latter part of the study is being performed with our research partners, Arctur and IBM Research.

5.2.1.6 What will happen to me if I decide to take part?

You will undergo the standard way of having your planned procedure as is the best current practice. All routine evaluations will be performed the same way as everyone else. In addition, some time during your procedure will be spent looking closely at your tissues before, during and after the administration of a dye called indocyanine green (ICG). This gives a measure of the local blood supply that can be visualised using a particular wavelength of light energy (“near-infrared”) built into the camera used during the operation. This allows flow patterns to be seen in a process called Intraoperative Fluorescence Angiography (IFA), which has been clinically used for several years now and has an excellent safety record. We have previously shown that this dye seems to pass through cancer tissue at a different rate compared to normal tissue. However, as the images on the screen can generate quite rapidly and are sometimes too complicated to easily understand by watching alone, we have developed processes, including software, to understand better what the various signals mean. To fully prove this, and make a usable system for the future, once the dye has been injected, we will start recording the images this camera sees. This analysis will need comparison with facts related to the results of the standard tests performed around your operation and your outcome afterwards. This will add approximately 10 minutes to your operation. Right now, any new information won’t impact or influence your care.

We have already carried out a similar study in the Mater Hospital, Dublin, Ireland, which showed that the analysis system could tell the difference between cancer and non-cancer cells. In this study, we now want to demonstrate this on a larger scale by including more patients in different hospitals.

Although your clinical team thinks you might be suitable to take part, they may still need to ask you some questions about your medical history and medications to see if you are suitable for the study. No additional or special tests are needed to check if you can take part in this study. The information needed should all be part of your routine care. The study does not determine the type of operation you will receive or how the operation will be carried out. All routine investigations (blood tests, biopsies and x-rays) will be carried out as per the current standard of care. For participants undergoing diagnostic evaluation only, we will require blood samples for haematology and biochemistry to be taken prior to intervention. Tissue biopsies will be taken during your surgical procedure for research purposes.

The pictures from your operation will be recorded and stored and may be transferred with some other clinical data to collaborating research teams in University College Dublin, Arctur, Slovenia and IBM Research, Dublin. Shared recordings will have all identifying information removed. The only information we will use is already being kept as routine as part of your planned procedure, and generated during the research study. You will not be asked to come into the hospital for any extra clinic visits.

5.2.1.7 What will happen to my Samples and Data?

Suppose you decide to participate in the study. In that case, the information collected about you will be handled and stored in accordance with the consent that you have given and also the Data Protection Act 2018. The Mater Misericordiae University Hospital and the UCD Clinical Research Centre (CRC) will be the Data Controllers for the study. Data Controllers must ensure the information collected about you for the study is looked after and used properly.

Arctur and IBM Research are Data Processors for this research study. As the study progresses, it's possible that other partners and collaborators will join the study, and information may be shared with them- however, no personal information will be shared outside of the hospital and the CRC.

Study team members will collect medical and healthcare information about you that is needed for the study. This information is called your personal and healthcare data. It will be collected on paper forms from you and your medical notes. You will be given a study number. This number will be used with your date of birth and initials to identify you on each paper form. Information collected which could identify you will be held securely with strict arrangements about who can access the information. Your data will be entered into a secure database held at the CRC.

Tissue samples taken as part of your routine clinical care will be stored in the Mater Hospital as part of your patient record – this is standard practice regardless of whether you are participating in a trial or not.

For patients who are deemed clinically suitable, an additional biopsy of the tumour may be taken. Up to four additional samples may be taken, depending on tumour size, following fluorescence analysis if it is felt it will not compromise the removal of the tumour. The aim of taking these samples is to assess the variation in tissue type (cancer vs non-cancer) in different areas of the polyp and how this compares to different areas of fluorescence. These biopsies will be analysed in the pathology lab and the samples discarded following analysis. These samples will not be shared with anyone else in the future for other studies.

Your healthcare records may be looked at by authorised individuals from the research team, ethics committee or regulatory authorities to check that the study is being carried out correctly, without violating your confidentiality.

- Shared information will be anonymised (for example, your full name will not be disclosed). The information will only be used for healthcare research and cannot be used to contact you, affect your care or make decisions about future services available to you, such as insurance.
- Your data will be passed to other organisations participating in this study (including in other countries where the data protection standards and laws are different to Ireland's) to monitor the study; this data will have your name removed.
- Videos of the part of your operation using the dye will be sent to the research teams in Arctur and IBM Research, along with clinical data. These will be sent via standard processes (electronic transfer, standard mail or courier). Your name or any identifying features will not be sent alongside this. Your video will be identified by a study ID or code – the key to this code will not leave UCD.
- UCD will keep identifiable information about you for a maximum of 10 years after the study has finished. Your rights to access, change or move your information are limited as we need to manage your information in specific ways in order for the research to be reliable and accurate. To safeguard your rights, we will use the minimum personally-identifiable information possible. If you withdraw from the study, we will keep the information about you that we have already obtained.

If you wish to raise a complaint about how we have handled your personal data, you can contact our Data Protection Officer, who will investigate the matter. You can contact our Data Protection Officer at:

Email: [\[insert local DPO email address\]](#)

Telephone number: [insert local DPO telephone number]

5.2.1.8 Are there any benefits to taking part in this research?

There will not be a specific benefit to you; however, using the dye to look at tissues during procedures may or may not improve surgery and results in future. You will be monitored regularly and closely

throughout the study. It is hoped that by participating, you are helping progress our knowledge and treatments for future patients.

5.2.1.9 Are there any risks to me or others if I take part?

Your doctor has recommended that you have an investigation or surgical procedure for your suspected or confirmed cancer diagnosis. You will receive this care whether or not you take part in this study. Your clinical team aims to ensure that any risks are kept to a minimum. Therefore, the risks are largely the same inside or outside the study. There is a slight additional risk from the administration of the dye, including a possible severe allergic reaction. However, this occurs rarely and less than 1 in every 10,000 times the drug is used. Patients who have a history of iodide allergy should not partake in this trial as ICG contains sodium iodide. In addition ICG can interact with certain medications including anti-epileptic medications, methadone and certain antibiotics. Please let us know what regular medications you take so we can ensure no reaction will occur. Some extra time is being taken during your procedure, and some additional tissue samples may be taken too. Great care will be taken to ensure the confidentiality of your data, and the risk to participants of a breach of confidentiality is considered very low.

5.2.1.10 What happens if something goes wrong when I'm taking part in the study?

The Study Management Group will closely monitor the study on an ongoing basis. This will ensure that any problems are seen as soon as possible, and the study can be changed or stopped if necessary. If you experience problems, you must report these to the study team. Your clinical team will review you after your operation, as is standard practice. Your participation in the study may be terminated without your consent for reasons such as participation not being in your best interest.

5.2.1.11 Will I be told the outcome of the study? Will I be told the results of any tests or investigations performed as part of this study that relates to me?

We expect it to take approximately four years to complete this study, so the results are unlikely to impact your own care directly. When the study is complete, a report will be prepared. The results may be published in a medical journal and presented at medical conferences, but no individual participants will be identified. The results may also be summarised on the internet- these results will not identify any individual participants. If you would like to obtain a copy of the published results, you can contact a member of the research team.

5.2.2 Part 2 – Data Protection

The following information should also be included as standard in Participant Information Leaflets in order to ensure compliance with the 2018 Health Research Regulations.

5.2.2.1 What information about me (personal data) will be used as part of this study? Will my medical records be accessed?

We will need to access your medical records as part of this study. Members of your clinical team will share the relevant details with the research team at UCD. All details shared will be kept to the minimum required to carry out the study. You will be assigned a study ID number – this means that we do not need to share identifiable details such as your name and hospital number with the team in UCD. However, details such as your previous endoscopy reports, laboratory results, medications and past medical history need to be shared to ensure our study results are reliable.

Following initial analysis by the team in UCD, all your data will be fully anonymised before sharing with any other partners.

5.2.2.2 What will happen to my personal data?

Your data will be pseudo-anonymised before sharing it with UCD, the data controllers. This means that identifying features such as your name and hospital number will be removed. You will instead be assigned a trial number. This data will be analysed by the research team and then further anonymised prior to sharing it with the data processor Arctur, a software development company based in Slovenia and also IBM Research. Arctur will not be able to trace the data being shared back to you. Arctur will use your videos and the outcome of your pathology reports to create a software programme that will be able to detect cancer within a polyp/tumour based on the flow patterns of the dye. UCD will also analyse the videos to make sure that the software is working correctly and to the standard that we have already seen possible in the previous initial study. This software “learns” about the differences between cancer and non-cancer cells based on what it has seen in the videos of your surgery and those of other patients. It is hoped that in the future, the software can apply this “knowledge” to detect cancers in other patients. Your data will help form the basis for this “knowledge”. Your data will not be used for purposes other than the development of this software, and it will not be processed in any way that could cause damage or distress to you.

Your data will be kept at UCD in a pseudo-anonymised format for the duration of the study and for ten years after the publication of the results. This is part of good scientific practice to ensure that any queries that arise over the results of the study can be reviewed. When it is time to destroy your data, this will be done in accordance with all legal and ethical requirements and with particular concern for confidentiality and security.

5.2.2.3 Who will access and use my personal data as part of this study?

Professor Ronan Cahill, consultant surgeon at the Mater Hospital and a Professor at UCD, is the study’s principal investigator. He and his research team at the Clinical Research Centre at UCD will have access to your personal data, including details from your medical records.

Your anonymised data will be shared with the data processor Arctur, based in Slovenia and IBM Research, Dublin.

5.2.2.4 Will my personal data be kept confidential? How will my data be kept safe?

Your privacy is important to us. We take steps to make sure we protect your confidentiality and keep your data safe. Here are some examples of how we do this. All the individuals involved in this research study have been provided with training in data protection law. Only the minimum amount of data required for the study will be retrieved from your medical notes. Paper data collected from your notes and the pictures and videos taken during surgery will be pseudo-anonymised (all identifying features removed) before processing at the CRC. The number of staff processing your data will be kept to a minimum. All staff accessing your data adhere to a professional code of conduct to maintain confidentiality. Your data will be pseudo-anonymised prior to sharing it with the external data processor, in whose hands it will be anonymous. All the data processed for this study have been subjected to a risk assessment by the hospital and the university's GDPR offices. The level of risk associated with this study has been identified as low.

Ultimately we plan to present and publish this research in scientific forums. However, your data will not be identifiable from these presentations and publications.

5.2.2.5 What is the lawful basis for using my personal data?

By law², we can use your personal information for scientific research³ (in the public interest⁴). We will also ask for your consent to use your data as a requirement of the Irish Health Research Regulations.

5.2.2.6 What are my rights?

As a data subject, you have specific rights. You are entitled to:

- access to your data and receive a copy of it
- restrict or object to the processing of your data
- object to any further processing of the information we hold about you
- have inaccurate information about you corrected or deleted
- receive your data in a portable format and have it transferred to another data controller
- request deletion of your data

By law, you can exercise the following rights in relation to your personal data unless the request would make it impossible or very difficult to conduct the research. You can exercise these rights by contacting your study Doctor, Professor. Cahill or the UCD Data Protection Officer, gdpr@ucd.ie or the [insert hospital] Data Protection Officer, [insert DPO email address]

² The European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

³ Article 9 (2)(j)

⁴ Article 6 (1)(g,i)

5.2.3 Part 3 – Costs, Funding and Approval

5.2.3.1 Has this study been approved by a research ethics committee?

****Approval is pending. This section is a draft response to be submitted as part of the application. ****

Yes, this study has been approved by the [insert hospital name] Ethics Committee. Approval was granted on xx/10/2022. No members of the research team have a link to the committee.

5.2.3.2 Who is organising and funding this study? Will the results be used for commercial purposes?

The Clinical Research Centre of University College Dublin is conducting this research. Funding has been awarded by the European Union through the Horizon Europe Programme. This is the EU's key funding programme for research and innovation.

The results of the study will be disclosed for scientific purposes. It is planned that this study will result in a prototype device that can be used to differentiate cancer cells. However, this device would require significant further research and development prior to consideration of commercialisation.

5.2.3.3 Is there any payment for taking part? Will it cost me anything if I agree to take part?

No, we are not paying patients to take part in the study. It is not anticipated that you will require any additional hospital visits as a result of this study. Should you need to make any additional visits to the hospital as a result of the study, please don't hesitate to get in touch with a member of the research team. You will be reimbursed for travel expenses.

5.2.4 Part 4 – Future Research

5.2.4.1 Will my personal data and/or biological material be used in future studies?

To continue to broaden our knowledge in the area of cancer and bowel disease, we may share information collected about you for this study with other research teams and collaborators, including in industry, to answer new research questions in the future and to allow what we learn to be put into clinical practice. In order to share your data with researchers outside this study, we need your consent. These researchers may work at University College Dublin or at another organisation, such as another university or company involved in health and care research. They may be in this country or abroad, including countries outside the European Economic Area ('EEA'). The data protection laws outside of the EEA may not be as comprehensive as within the EEA. For transfers of your anonymised data to third parties outside of the EEA, we take additional steps in line with Data Protection Legislation to ensure adequate safeguards for protecting your privacy, fundamental rights and freedoms are in place.

Shared information will be anonymised (for example, your name will not be disclosed). Information will only be shared for research and will not be used to contact you, affect your care or make decisions about future services available to you, such as insurance. Any future studies may only take place if they have received research ethics approval. In either case, you can withdraw your consent at any time without consequences.

5.2.5 Part 5 – Further Information

5.2.5.1 Who should I contact for information or complaints?

If you have any concerns or questions, you can contact:

- Principal Investigator:

Prof. Ronan Cahill,

Professor of Surgery and Consultant General Surgeon, Mater Misericordiae
University Hospital, Eccles Street, Dublin 7

01-8545091

- Data Protection Officer of [insert hospital name]:

[DPO address]

[DPO email]

[DPO telephone number]

- Data Protection Officer of University College Dublin:

gdpr@ucd.ie

Under GDPR, if you are not satisfied with how your data is being processed, you have the right to lodge a complaint with the Office of the Data Protection Commission, 21 Fitzwilliam Square South, Dublin 2, Ireland. Website: www.dataprotection.ie.

5.2.5.2 Will I be contacted again?

No. We will not need to contact you following your operation. However, as is standard practice, you will have a follow-up appointment with your clinical team.

5.3 Appendix 3 - Consent form

<p>STUDY NAME:</p> <p>Centre ID:</p> <p>Identification Number for study:</p>

Consent Form

<p>The below section should always be included in consent forms. The consent should be reviewed by the Principal Investigator and research team and amended as appropriate in line with the specific requirements and consents being sought from participants.</p>	
<p>There are 3 sections in this form. Each section has a statement and asks you to initiate it if you agree. The end of this form is for the researchers to complete.</p> <p>Please ask <u>any</u> questions you may have when reading each of the statements.</p> <p>Thank you for participating.</p> <p>Please <u>Initial</u> the box if you agree with the statement. Please feel free to ask questions if there is something you do not understand.</p>	
General	Tick box
I confirm I have read and understood the Information Leaflet for the above study. The information has been fully explained to me, and I have been able to ask questions, all of which have been answered to my satisfaction.	
I understand that this study is entirely voluntary, and if I decide that I do not want to take part, I can stop taking part in this study at any time without giving a reason. I understand that deciding not to take part will not affect my future medical care.	
I understand that my medical notes and records may be looked at by Prof. Cahill and his study team at UCD, where it is relevant to the research. I agree that these individuals can access my records. I understand that all information will be kept private and confidential and that my name will not be disclosed.	
I understand that I will not be paid for taking part in this study.	

I know how to contact the research team if I need to.	
I agree to participate in this research study, having been fully informed of the risks, benefits and alternatives which are set out in full in the information leaflet I have been provided with.	
I agree to be contacted by researchers by phone and/or post as part of this research study.	
Data processing	Tick box
I agree to allow personal information about me to be shared with third parties, including national and international hospitals, and academic research institutions, for the purpose of colorectal cancer research, as described in the Information leaflet.	
I understand that personal information about me will be protected in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation.	
I understand that there are no direct benefits to me from participating in this study. I understand that results from the analysis of my personal information will not be given to me.	
I understand that I can stop taking part in this study at any time without giving a reason, and this will not affect my future medical care.	

Remove the table below if it does not apply to your study – this table will only apply if you placed the paragraph entitled ‘Consent to Future Uses’ in your Information Leaflet		
FUTURE USE OF INFORMATION		
RETENTION OF RESEARCH SAMPLES IN THE FUTURE [please choose one or more as you see fit]	Y	N
OPTION 1: I give permission for my personal information to be stored for <i>possible future research related</i> to the current study (CLASSICA: Validating AI in Classifying Cancer in Real-Time Surgery <i>without further consent</i> being required but only if the research is approved by a Research Ethics Committee.		
OPTION 2: I agree that future research projects into colorectal cancer may be carried out by researchers working for <u>commercial/pharmaceutical companies.</u>		

I, the undersigned, have taken the time to fully explain to the above patient the nature and purpose of this study in a way that they could understand. I have explained the risks and possible benefits involved. I have invited them to ask questions on any aspect of the study that concerned them.

I have given a copy of the information leaflet and consent form to the participant with contacts of the study team

Researcher name

Title and qualifications

Signature

Date

| | |

3 copies to be made: 1 for patient, 1 for PI and 1 for hospital records.

1. Cahill RA, O'Shea DF, Khan MF, Khokhar HA, Epperlein JP, Mac Aonghusa PG, et al. Artificial intelligence indocyanine green (ICG) perfusion for colorectal cancer intra-operative tissue classification. Br J Surg. 2021;108(1):5-9.